

Mathematical Expectations on Frequency and Probability Distributions

Chinnaraji Annamalai
School of Management, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, India
Email: anna@iitkgp.ac.in
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0992-2584>

Abstract: Mathematical Expectation of a random variable is the average value taken by the random variable over random events. Random variable plays a vital role in AI and machine learning. Actually, a random variable is a variable whose possible values are numerical outcomes of a random phenomenon. This paper discusses the mathematical expectation of the random variable among frequency distribution and probability distribution.

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1. Introduction

Mathematical Expectation, (also called mean, expected value, expectancy, expectation operator, or first moment), of a random variable is the average value taken by the random variable over random phenomena. A random variable with Gaussian distribution [1] is said to be normally distributed and plays a vital role in AI and machine learning.

2. Mathematical Expectation

A random variable is a variable whose numerical values are assumed by random events. Let X be a discrete random variable which assumes the values $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ with respective frequencies $f_1, f_2, f_3, \dots, f_n$. The frequency distribution ($x, f(x)$) of the random variable X is shown by the following table:

$X:$	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_n
$f:$	f_1	f_2	f_3	f_n

The mean of the frequency distribution is given by

$$\bar{x} = \frac{f_1x_1 + f_2x_2 + f_3x_3 + \dots + f_nx_n}{N}, \text{ where } N \text{ is the total frequency.}$$
$$\bar{x} = \frac{f_1}{N}x_1 + \frac{f_2}{N}x_2 + \frac{f_3}{N}x_3 + \dots + \frac{f_n}{N}x_n.$$

Here, the probability of X is denoted by

$$P(X = x_i) = \frac{f_i}{N} = p_i; \quad i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n.$$

The probability distribution ($x, P(X = x)$) of the random variable X is shown by the following table:

$X:$	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_n
$P(X = x):$	p_1	p_2	p_3	p_n

Now, the mathematical expectation of X or expected value of X , denoted by $E(X)$, is defined by

$$E(X) = \bar{X} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i = \sum_{i=1}^n p_i x_i, \quad \text{where } \sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1.$$

Here, the mathematical expectation $E(X)$ refers to the mean of the frequency distribution.

A theorem on mean in terms of expectation is given by:

$$E(aX + b) = aE(X) + b, \text{ where } a \text{ and } b \text{ are constants.}$$

Proof. Let X be a discrete random variable which assumes the values $x_1, x_2, x_3, \dots, x_n$ with respective probabilities $p_1, p_2, p_3, \dots, p_n$.

Then, $E(aX + b) = p_1(ax_1 + b) + p_2(ax_2 + b) + p_3(ax_3 + b) + \dots + p_n(ax_n + b)$

$$E(aX + b) = a(p_1x_1 + p_2x_2 + p_3x_3 + \dots + p_nx_n) + b(p_1 + p_2 + p_3 + \dots + p_n)$$

$$E(aX + b) = a \sum_{i=1}^n p_i x_i + b \sum_{i=1}^n p_i = aE(X) + b, \left(\because \sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1 \right).$$

$$\therefore E(aX + b) = aE(X) + b.$$

Note that $E(cX) = c$ and $E(aX - b) = aE(X) - b$, where a, b , and c are constants.

Addition theorem on Expectations: The mathematical expectation of the sum of independent random variable is equal to the sum of their expectations. For any two of independent random variables X and Y , $E(X + Y) = E(X) + E(Y)$.

Multiplication theorem on Expectations: The mathematical expectation of the product of independent random variable is equal to the product of their expectations. For any two of independent random variables X and Y , $E(XY) = E(X)E(Y)$.

Variance of X in terms of Expectation is given by

$$\sigma_x^2 = \text{Var}(X) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 = E[X - \bar{X}]^2$$

$$\therefore \sigma_x^2 = E[X - E(X)]^2, \left(\because \bar{X} = E(X) = \text{Mean} \right)$$

Here, $E[X - \bar{X}]^2$ is the mean of $(X - \bar{X})^2$ since $E(X) = \bar{X}$ which is the mean of X .

$$\text{Also, } \sigma_x^2 = \text{Var}(X) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^n f_i x_i^2 - (\bar{X})^2 = E(X^2) - [E(X)]^2$$

$$\therefore \text{Variance of } X = \sigma_x^2 = \text{Var}(X) = E[X - E(X)]^2 = E(X^2) - [E(X)]^2.$$

A theorem on variance in terms of expectation is given by:

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = a^2 \text{Var}(X), \text{ where } a, b, \text{ and } c \text{ are constants.}$$

Let us prove this theorem as follows:

We know that $\sigma_x^2 = \text{Var}(X) = E[X - E(X)]^2$.

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = E[(aX + b) - E(aX + b)]^2 = E[aX + b - aE(X) - b]^2.$$

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = E[aX + b - aE(X) - b]^2, \quad (\because E(aX + b) = aE(X) + b).$$

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = E[aX + b - aE(X) - b]^2 = E[a\{X - E(X)\}]^2.$$

$$\text{Var}(aX + b) = a^2E[X - E(X)]^2 = a^2\text{Var}(X)$$

Note that $\text{Var}(c) = 0$, $\text{Var}(X \pm c) = \text{Var}(X)$, and $\text{Var}(aX \pm b) = a^2\text{Var}(X)$, where a , b , and c are constants.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the author discussed more about the mathematical expectation of random variables and its properties and theorems in connecting with the mean and the variance of the random variables. These details can enable the researchers to be involved in the scientific research on computing and mathematical sciences.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2024) The Gaussian Integral for the Normal Distribution in Machine Learning. *Cambridge Open Engage, Cambridge University Press*.
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